

Effectiveness of Prison-based Vocational Training Programs for Female Inmates in Sri Lanka: Trainers' Perspectives

E. M. V. O. Ekanayake¹, L A Pavithra Madhuwanthi²

^{1,2} Department of Public Administration, University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Sri Lanka

ABSTRACT: This study intends to evaluate the effectiveness of vocational training programs for female inmates in Sri Lanka. This is a qualitative study based on vocational training programs conducted for female inmates in Dumbara (New Bogambara) and Kalutara prisons in Sri Lanka. The study used primary data and semi-structured in-depth interviews which were conducted with trainers engaged in providing vocational training programs for the female inmates in the chosen two prisons. Purposive sampling method was used. Data collection was carried out during September 2020 and due to the Covid-19 pandemic, access to the trainers was highly restricted and thereby the study was limited to interview only four trainers. Thematic analysis was adopted for data analysis. The trainers emphasized on seven themes regarding the effectiveness of vocational training programs conducted for the female inmates in the selected two prisons in Sri Lanka. Good organizational support for vocational training programs, positive reaction from female inmates to take the trainings, creating opportunities for female inmates to expand their learning and help inmates to find self-employment opportunities, learning and behavioural changes among the inmates, promoting inter relationships among the female inmates, offering of effective incentive system for female inmates, cost avoidance in the prison. Findings implied that the effective conduct of vocational training programs for the female inmates is beneficial for the inmates, prison authorities and ultimately for the society at large.

KEYWORDS: Effectiveness, Vocational training programs, Female inmates, Prisons, Trainers

1. INTRODUCTION

Rehabilitation and reformation of offenders is one of the core functions of the Prisons Service. An inmate is a person, who is confined to an institution such as a prison or hospital [1]. The lives of them should not be limited to the space of their cells, but should be explored by the world. With the identification of government responsibility towards civilizing inmates to the society, a considerable attention of prison authorities has been drawn on conducting several types of programs. The provisioning of vocational training programs for inmates is one program which provides a greater support for inmates to strengthen their economic and social conditions. In Sri Lankan context, the Department of Prisons has made arrangements to conduct vocational trainings for the inmates. According to the performance report of Department of Prisons, in the year of 2018, allocation for vocational training programs in Sri Lankan prisons was Rs.3, 500, 000 [2]. Though a considerable amount of provision is made by the effectiveness of vocational training programs conducted in Sri Lankan prisons is somewhat questionable. A Nigerian prison study implies the need for assessing the effectiveness of vocational training programs conducted in the prisons by stating that prison system needs to be in a more progressive manner, to enable inmates to have ultimate rehabilitation through training in vocational skills. This will enhance an effective and a proper inmates' reintegration into the society. If these vocational trainings are effective in prisons to be efficiently utilized by the inmates, it will enhance their reintegration into the society, and reduce recidivism by empowering them [3]. This research was intended to focus on the experiences and perspectives of trainers who engage in providing vocational training programs for the female inmates, by using interviews and identifying themes for evaluating the effectiveness of vocational training programs conducted for female inmates in Sri Lanka. However the findings were not expected to generalize. The study is significant as it focused on a neglected area in the society and it is about evaluating the effectiveness of a government activity. As the research implications for further research, use of a larger sample size and conducting research with the inmates are suggested.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Vocational Training Programs for the Inmates

Vocational education in general can be considered as one of the most widely implemented and evaluated types of correctional intervention. The main purpose of provisioning of vocational education programs is to counteract the effects of poor educational achievement and lowered employability commonly found among correctional populations [4].

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In the research report presented by RAND Corporation in US on "Evaluating the Effectiveness of Correctional Education" has identified several importance of having correctional education for the inmates. Correctional education improves inmates' chances of not returning to prison, it may improve their chances of obtaining employment after release and providing correctional education can be cost-effective when it comes to reducing recidivism [5].

Arditi et al. (1973) revealed on types of vocational training programs offered to the inmates based on their gender. The researchers found that female inmates were only offered training in, cosmetology, floral design, food service, garment manufacturing and housekeeping etc. and the male inmates, were offered programs in air conditioning repair, auto mechanics, baking, carpentry, electronics, farming, horticulture, and many more [6]. It could be observed female inmates are given access to a limited number of varieties in vocational training programs than the men.

Kuruppu (2001) referred to the Sri Lankan prison context and stated that, every convicted inmate is required to work for approximately eight hours a day. This is including both vocational training in industries as well as on job training in prison workshops. And there are wide variety of trainings are provided for the prisoners such as carpentry, masonry, laundry, motor mechanism, printing, tailoring, weaving, soap making, mat making, brush making, bread making and the manufacture of coir goods etc. for male inmates whilst the convicted female inmates are given training in vocations such as tailoring, knitting, weaving and cookery [7].

2.2 Evaluating the Effectiveness of Vocational Training Programs Conducted for the Inmates

In the report on 'Evaluating the Effectiveness of Correctional Education', it identified the vocational education is one type of correctional education for inmates and it identified four criterion in order to evaluate the effectiveness of such correctional programs conduct in the prisons. Relationship between correctional education and recidivism, relationship between correctional education and employment and relationship between computer-assisted instruction and academic performance and comparison of the costs of correctional education programs and reincarceration costs are the four criterions used [8].

Sachithra and Wijewardhana (2020) have identified few aspects of effective vocational training programs for inmates such as having a mechanism to facilitates the selection of inmates for appropriate training and to assess whether it is transparent, fair, reasonable and open and enabling the inmates' to expressed preferences. And the scholars further added that in order to improve the effectiveness adequate provisions should be made and these should be accessible to the inmates [9].

4-level model presented by Kirkpatrick (1996) over evaluating training programs consists of four criterions that can be applied in the context of evaluating the effectiveness of vocational training programs conduct in the prisons. The four levels or the evaluation criterion are as follows;

1. Reaction - measuring the interest, motivation, and attention levels of participants.
2. Learning - measuring what participants have learned in terms of both knowledge and/or skills
3. Behavior - performance or ability to use learned knowledge or skills
4. Results - measuring of the impact that the training has had overall, including financial or morale impacts [10].

In the article, "The "Black Box" Behind Prison-Based Vocational Training Programs" following criteria were identified in order to measure the effectiveness of vocational training programs conduct in prisons.

1. Reduce the risk that ex-prisoners will return to crime after their release from prison
2. Give inmates valuable work experience
3. Improve their employment opportunities after they are released from prison [11].

And especially about the vocational training programs conducting for female inmates, the effectiveness can be measured in terms of criterion such as; vocational skills training programs should be chosen and designed with consideration for the types of jobs women are likely to be offered, with a view to breaking gender stereotypes and economic disparities in the job market. Importantly, prisoners should also have a choice as to the type of training program they would like to join. They should be trained according to recognized national standards and receive accredited qualifications for their learning [12].

2.3 A Theory on Evaluating the Effectiveness of Vocational Training Programs

A research study conducted by Manchester Metropolitan University of UK has developed a rough, initial general theory of prison education articulated in the form of three context-mechanism-outcome configuration (CMO). Then it has been tested by assessing the desistance literature: 'hook', 'safe space' and 'qualifications'. 'Hook' refers to engaging in prison education as a 'hook for change' and its impact on personal identity. 'Safe space' refers to the space an educational class can provide and its relevance to social identity. 'Qualifications' refers to the relevance of skills and qualifications gains [13]. As vocational training is a part of the prison education, this theory can be applied to the context of evaluating the effectiveness of the vocational training programs conduct for prisoners. And this theory can be explained as the following Table 1_CMO theory;

Table 1_CMO theory

Theme	Context	Mechanism	Outcome
Hook	Prisoners require structural opportunities that can act as a 'hook for change' if they are to desist.	Education is, in and of itself, a 'hook' for change as it develops new interests, provides activity etc.	Prisoners diverted away from antisocial activities
Qualifications	Prisoners do not perceive opportunities as being available to them and therefore fail to take advantage of structural opportunities	Educational progress and achievements such as qualifications gain means the individual has an increased belief that they can move forward, develop and access opportunity	Prisoners take up structural opportunities more often which, in turn, increases rates of employment
Safe space	Crime is correlated with low self-control and poor empathy.	As a collective involvement happens it facilitates to understand peers and their cultures. And they can have discussions with each other on their motivations and issues.	Prisoners develop a better understanding of other people reducing their likelihood to commit crimes.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study is a qualitative study which is conducted as a case study research during the year 2020. And this is focused on two cases of vocational training practices in Dumbara (New Bogambara) and Kalutara prisons. The population in this study refers to the trainers who provide vocational trainings for female inmates. The sample is consisted of four female trainers involved in providing vocational training programs for female inmates and it was drawn using purposive sampling method. The data collection was done through the use of the telephone interview method. An Interview guide was used to identify the basic demographic information of the participants, their views on how effective the vocational training programs. Thematic analysis method was used as the data analysis method in this study.

4. DATA ANALYSIS

4.1 Sample in Brief

The sample of the study is consisted of four female trainers who have engaged in providing vocational trainings for the female inmates. Among the participants Participant 1 and Participant 2 worked in the Kaluthara prison before the lockdown in Covid-19 pandemic situation. As currently the female section has been transferred, both Participant 1 and 2 have expressed their past experiences with regards to the vocational training programs conducted for the female inmates. And the Participant 3 and Participant 4 represent the Dumbara prison and both of them are currently engaging in providing the trainings for the female inmates. And little other basic information about the participants in the study can be shown as in the

Table 2_Basic information of the participants to the study.

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Participants (Trainers)	Type of employment	Years of service	Qualifications	Number of trainees under the supervision	Types of training provide
01	Employed by a NGO	3 years	Followed patchwork, hand embroidery and tailoring courses	16	Paper crafts, Bag creation, Ribbon works, Pillow case designing

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02	Vocational instructor (VI)	5 years	Followed a dress making/tailoring course	15	Saree jacket, Skirts, Baby suits, Night dresses
03	A jailor specially trained for conducting the trainings	6 years	Followed a batik and a tailoring courses &	20	Batik saree, Lungi, Batik sarongs, Batik housecoats
04	Vocational instructor (VI)	5 years	Completed 2 years diploma	33	Handloom sarees, lungi, Suits of the inmates, Towels

Note: Due to the Covid -19 pandemic and the increasing number of male inmates, the female section of the Kalutara prison has now been moved. The both participant 1 and participant 2 have expressed their past experiences.

4.2 Effectiveness of Vocational Training Programs for Female Inmates in Sri Lanka

In order to satisfy the first research objective of evaluating the effectiveness of vocational training programs conducted for female inmates, seven themes were being used in order to get the insights of the participants to the study in this regards as. These themes or the criterion for evaluating the effectiveness can be named as; organizational support for effective vocational training programs for the female inmates, reaction of inmates towards the training programs, learning and behavior of inmates in the training programs, self-employment by ex-inmates, promotion of inter-relationships through the training programs, cost avoidance by the vocational training programs and the effectiveness of incentives provided for the inmates.

4.2.1 Organizational support for conducting effective vocational training programs for the female inmates

For having effective vocational training programs in the prison, supportive organizational commitment is a must. The relevant authorities have their responsibility to provide the required facilities, direct the inmates to take the trainings and to make a favorable environment to conduct these trainings. In order to carry out more effective vocational training programs a significant contribution has been made from the Department of Prisons, where separate locations and all the required resources are provided in a sufficient manner.

In order to effective training programs to be happened, the participation of the inmates is also essential. The prison officials should encourage inmates to take these training programs. The trainer from the NGO stated that due to the less number of target participants that were pre-determined, prison authority has taken a step forward to expand the opportunity for the inmates outside the target group. And she added that it would not be worth enough to send a trainer outside the prison if there are a less number of recipients to the service

“The main aim of our NGO by conducting such training programs targeted on the convicted female inmates who are having children below the age five. But due to the lower number of such type of inmates prison officials made a special provision to make it possible for the other convicted and the unconvicted or remand prisoners” (Participant 1).

And in some cases, participants to certain types of training programs might have to be pre-selected in order to deliver an effective program. Because, there are some training programs that require participants to be physically fit and some may require mathematical skills etc. Participant 2 discussed about the criterion for selection of the inmates for the training program on tailoring as: *“Inmates should physically fit to engage in these programs. Inmates who are having problems with their vision and elderly inmates are not encouraged to take the tailoring training program. Also they should have basic level mathematics capabilities”* (Participant 2).

4.2.2 Reaction of inmates over the vocational training programs

The level one of Kirkpatrick model which is being used to assess the effectiveness of vocational training is “reaction”. It is about the trainees’ feelings for and liking of a training program [14]. And in here, it could be identified as the trainee’s motivation to learn. And it is assessed in terms of their participation, willingness and motivation. In this study it is found that inmates are having a higher level of participation, willingness and motivation to take these vocational training programs

In terms of the participation, it can be assessed in terms of the attendance of the inmates for the trainings, being on time and their ability to tolerate the duration of the sessions. As expressed by the all trainers, most of the inmates are daily attendants except in some occasions like attending courts and health clinics etc. And also most of the time the inmates are on time to the place where the training is taking place and it seems they participate very enthusiastically.

“My training sessions are conducting in all weekdays from 6.45a.m.to 11.30a.m.and resume from 1.30p.m.to 4.15p.m. And I highly appreciate the inmates’ participation as they are on time and not complaining about the length of the training program” (Participant 4).

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Willingness of the inmates towards these types of programs can be varied. There may be inmates who are really willing to take these trainings with their understanding about the importance and the benefits they could obtain through the participation of the vocational training programs. In the interviews, it was found that, inmates have a desire to experience the different creative things and to get new knowledge. And they are more interested about what is the new knowledge trainers bring. And those inmates with a previously learned knowledge have a high level of will to exhibit their talents to their co-inmates and to their trainers. And the trainers are generous enough to express their ideas and give them a space to incorporate their knowledge and creativity for the creations they make at the trainings.

"In my classes, there was an inmate who good at wool crafts. She suggested on using wool crafts during the trainings. We made key-tags using wool dolls and it was very popular among the inmates" (Participant 1).

When it refers to the motivation of the inmates over taking these vocational training programs, there could be different motives of the inmates such as motivation to acquire new knowledge, desire for receiving the incentives and there could be more. The trainers have experienced that, the inmates are having an intention to show their skills to others and especially to their family members. The participant 1 shared her own experience as; *"in the paper crafts making training I found one inmate who was doing these paper works enthusiastically. And she happily expressed that she could teach these paper crafts to her daughter who was in the nursery"* And for the convicted prisoners, the main motivation to take these trainings can be identified as the home leaves they received. As stated by both participant 1 and 2, the convicted prisoners are entitled to receive home leaves around 7 to 10 days to pay a visit to their home and return. And one main criterion that considered with this regard is the inmates' participation for the vocational training programs. *"Depend on the inmates' imprisoned time they are given home leaves and it is mandatory for them to take the trainings conducted by the industrial sector of the prison. And it is considered as one criterion for offering them that privilege"* (Participant 4).

4.2.3 Learning and behavior of inmates

Learning, was defined as the principles, facts, and techniques understood and absorbed by the trainees. And behavior is defined as transferring knowledge, skills, and attitudes learned during the training to the job [15]. The effectiveness of these vocational training programs could be assessed against what participants have learned in terms of knowledge and/or skills from the vocational trainings provided to them and their ability to use the learned knowledge or skills.

As expressed by the all four participants in the study, even though many of the inmates have not any basic knowledge about these practices, all the inmates who participate in the training sessions had the ability to learn all the things teach in the sessions very quickly and easily and it is reflected in the products they made.

Many of the times the inmates are using their free time to come up with different creations. And it will lead for them to get a self-satisfaction about themselves. Then it will create an effective life for the inmate during their imprisoned time period. And also some creations made by the inmates are marketed by the prison authority and these products have their market share mainly because of the quality of the products made by the inmates. And as expressed by the trainers the products made by the inmates are in good quality where those could be marketed without any doubt. In the batik trainings, the inmates are trained on different batik creations and inmates are manufacturing them in the prison premises with the main purpose of marketing those products.

"Almost all of the products made by the inmates at the batik training are directed to the market and I must tell you that all those products are in good quality that accepts by the market" (Participant 3).

And also the inmates are using their learned knowledge for manufacturing the products for their own consumption. In the weaving trainings as stated by the Participant 4, inmates are trained for manufacturing handloom sarees and handloom lungi. And especially they are trained on manufacturing their own suits and few other clothing they need for their personal consumption. *"The female weaving section in Dumbara prison sews the prisoners' suits and the towels and bed sheets that are to be used by the inmates"* (Participant 4).

4.2.4 Self-employment by ex-inmates

Hendricks, 2001 emphasized that the ultimate goal of correctional education including vocational trainings and other education is to reduce recidivism by helping inmates become self-sufficient so that they can be re-integrated into society and become productive and successful workers, citizens, and family members [16]. And the participants in this study have disclosed their personal experiences about the self-employed ex-inmates.

"There is a lady who is still engaging in making children's clothes and sewing pillow cases. With the help of her relative she sells those in Pamunuwa market and earns a considerable income from that" (Participant 2). Accordingly, it can be viewed that the provisioning of the vocational training programs for the inmates, facilitates the inmates to earn an income through the engagement in the self-employment activities by practicing the knowledge they acquired from the trainings and they can get the support from their family members or from others to deliver more successful self-employment activity.

But both participant 3 and participant 4 expressed that there are no any records with them about the self-employed ex-inmates. Though there was relatively a less number of evidence regarding the self-employment by the ex-inmates, it can be stated that if

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inmates are truly believing in fair earnings, provisioning of vocational trainings would be much effective for them on their post release from the prison.

4.2.5 Promotion of inter relationships of the inmates

If inmates are maintaining sound relationships with others during the trainings it will create an effective environment to conduct these programs. All of the participants to the study expressed that inmates are highly corporative and supportive in the training programs. And some of them have experienced that inmates are willing to share their stories with their trainers.

"Sometimes they feel free to express their grievances with me. Some have spoken with me on their reasons caused for their imprisonment and they said that they are repenting" (Participant 1).

And also the inmates should maintain sound relationships with their co-inmates in their workings. According to the Criminal Justice Handbook by UNODC well-educated prisoners can play an important role in teaching their less skilled peers in a variety of countries. In the Indian state of Rajasthan, for example, graduate prisoners volunteer to teach fellow prisoners [17]. The participants have observed how the inmates maintain relationships with their peers. *"They are willing to share their knowledge with each other. Sometimes if one inmate missed the class in one day, in the other day she come to the class with the knowledge about what it was learnt in the previous class"* (Participant 1).

And also it can be viewed that the inmates possess the quality of respecting each other. And especially during the training sessions they exhibit their mutual understanding and the respect for their leaders. *"In some cases during the training we have to appoint a leader among the inmates. So we could see the rest of inmates listen to their leader and support her. And I have neither observed any rifts between the leader and the rest nor any rifts to be observed among the inmates"* (Participant 4).

4.2.6 Cost avoidance by the vocational training programs in the prison

When correctional programming can reduce misconduct, lower recidivism, and improve post-release employment outcomes, it can generate a monetary benefit to society, mostly through costs avoided from the prevention of crime [18]. For the maintenance purpose of the prisons, the government invests a huge amount of funds. And it could be in terms of staffing cost, utilities cost, costs for meals and for the clothing of the inmates and many other costs for the maintenance of the prison.

The all four participants to the study have emphasized that; the inmates could be entitled to have early release from the prison as per the requests by them. And for that the prison authority is considering about several facts of the inmates. The good behavior shown by the inmates within the prison premises could be one fact among them. When the convicted prisoners make their appeal to get release from the prison or to lessen their sentence, the good behavior of the inmates is one criterion considered by the prison authorities and by the courts.

"The inmates who maintain a good behavior in the prison may be considered by the prison authorities for lessen his or her term in the prison under the subject of law."(Participant 1).

The participation in the vocational training programs could help for the inmates to behave themselves well and to show their good behavior to others. And it will help them to reduce their term in prison. The participant 3, emphasized on how the vocational training programs could the help the inmates to maintain a good behavior within the prison. *"Inmates may not need to spend their time by gossiping with their co-inmates and quarrelling with them. They can spend their time meaningfully. So they can show a good behavior within the prison"*(Participant 3). Then ultimately it will cause to reduce the maintenance cost of the prison to a certain extent as the number of inmates imprisoned can be reduced

4.2.7 Effectiveness of incentives provided for the inmates

For the participation of the inmates to these training programs it could be found that they are given few monetary and non-monetary incentives. In terms of the monetary incentives, as described by both participant 3 and 4, there are special arrangements to deposit a certain amount of money in a bank account for the inmates who engaged in these programs

"50% of the profit we earned from the sales of batik products is deposited to the bank accounts of the inmates which are specially maintain for that purpose and the passbook is offered to the inmates at their release" (Participant 3).

And for the convicted inmates in the Dumbara prison, who are engaged in weaving practices are entitled to have a daily wage for their efforts.

And in terms of the non-monetary incentives, it was found that the prisoners are entitled to have home leaves and their effort is being valued by holding several exhibitions of the products they make. As stated by the trainers, in the trainings on batik, weaving and tailoring practices inmates are provided with a NVQ certificate at the completion of the training programs too. NVQ or the National vocational Qualification certificate is a nationally recognized that confirming one's skills in a particular occupation. And there is a view that NVQ level certificate holder could easily find an employment opportunity.

Accordingly it can be concluded that, the monetary incentives received by the inmates over taking these training programs would be an investment upon their release and the non-monetary incentives they received could increase their motivation. Especially, the certificate offered to them will give them recognition and also will increase their self-satisfaction.

5. DISCUSSION

The findings of the study have compared and contrasted with similar studies. The report on the Evaluating the Effectiveness of Correctional Education, it is identified vocational education is one type of correctional education for prisoners. And this study it has been used the criterion of The Relationship between Correctional Education and Recidivism, The Relationship between Correctional Education and Employment and The Relationship between computer-assisted instruction and academic performance [19]. In relation to these criterion, in our study it is been discussed mainly on the relationship between vocational education and the employment. And also can get a brief insight on the relationship between vocational education and recidivism. Moreover in here it is discussed about several other criterions in order to assess the effectiveness such as organizational support, reaction and learning and behavior of inmates, improvement of inter relationships of the inmates etc.

In a study conducted on “contemporary prison-based rehabilitation program in Sri Lanka” the researchers have discovered how the inmates perceive the effects of rehabilitation programs including the vocational training programs. There, the inmates have elaborated that these programs exhibit future employment opportunities for them and they identified the programs as future investment opportunities, as facilitation for mental relaxation and as a way to lessen their prison term. And some preferred to these programs as it allows them to disseminate their knowledge to others and some of them are interest about the incentives they are entitled to receive [20].

When these findings are compared to the current study, the motives of the female inmates to take part in these trainings are mostly similar to what the male inmates perceived about the vocational trainings they received. Though the study was conducted with the trainers than the inmates themselves, the trainers have elaborated on few aspects of perceptions of the female inmates towards these programs. It can be agreed with findings of the above research because it can be found that these programs can be considered as a future investment opportunity for the female inmates too and also it facilitate for the inmates to spend their free time fruitfully and facilitate their mental relaxation. But moreover, according to the knowledge of the trainers, the motivation of the female inmates to take these trainings may be due to the home leaves that they could obtain by showing good behavior in the prison.

And the findings of the study could be applied for comparing against the theory of context-mechanism-outcome configuration (CMO). As the ‘hook for change’ these trainings programs assist the inmates to construct a satisfying living condition mainly through the self-employment opportunities and thereby it could help the inmates to deviate from the antisocial activities to a certain extent. And under the “qualifications”, in this study it is found that in the Sri Lankan context the inmates are provided with a certificate for the completion of the training programs. And it helps to recognize the skills, achievements and the knowledge of the inmates which are obtained by participating in these trainings. And also the inmates could be recognized for the employment opportunities by the different employers. Under the theme “safe space”, it is assessed about how the inmates understand their peers. And in our study a criteria used as promotion of inter relationships of the inmates for the purpose of evaluating the effectiveness of such programs. There it was found that the inmates are maintaining good relationships with their co-inmates.

6. CONCLUSION

This thematic analysis is explored the effectiveness of the vocational training programs conducted for the female inmates in Sri Lanka. And it is carried out with four trainers who are engaged in providing vocational training programs for the female inmates. Based on the findings of the study in the analysis and the discussion chapter, following conclusions can be made with regards to the effectiveness of the vocational training programs conducted for female prisoners in Sri Lanka.

In order to carry out more effective vocational training programs in the prison premises a significant contribution has been made from the department of prisons where the separate locations and all the required resources are provided in a sufficient manner. And they are trying to increase the inmates' participation to the trainings and working on for improving the effectiveness of these programs. The inmates who are taking the trainings are having a higher level of liking for taking the vocational training programs conduct for them. They are exhibiting a good participation to the training programs and can find they are willing to take these trainings with having different motives.

And the inmates who taking the trainings are getting the benefits of these training programs by absorbing all the knowledge and skills and by using their capacity to deploy the learned knowledge and skills. They produce marketable products and products for their personal consumption. The knowledge gain from these programs will enable the ex-inmates to engage in self-employment opportunities and thereby they could strengthen their economy. And these training programs help the inmates to promote their inter-relationships with their co-inmates and as well as with the trainers.

From the organizational perspective, the provisioning of the vocational trainings for the inmates is a cost effective way which they could achieve through cost avoidance. The inmates who taking the trainings may have a chance of getting early release from the prison and thereby it will avoid the maintenance cost for the inmates. And for the inmates, they are provided with an effective incentive system in which they receive both monetary and non-monetary incentives and it give them an accumulated savings, recognition and value for their efforts.

REFERENCES

- 1) Oxford, p. U. (2020, January 27). *Definitions*. Retrieved from Oxford Learner's Dictionaries: <https://www.oxfordlearnersdictionaries.com/definition/english/prison?q=prison>
- 2) Department of Prisons. (2019, June 06). *Performance Report Department of Prisons- 2018*. Retrieved January 25, 2020, from www.parliament.lk: <https://www.parliament.lk/uploads/documents/paperspresented/performance-report-department-of-prison-2018.pdf>
- 3) ALIU, C. U. (2019). Effects of Adult Literacy Programme on Acquisition of Cake Baking Vocational Skills among Prison Inmates in Plateau State, Nigeria. *KIU Journal of Social Sciences*,5(2), 291–300.
- 4) Bouffard, J. A., Mackenzie, D. L., & Hickman, L. J. (2000). Effectiveness of Vocational Education and Employment Programs for Adult Offenders . *Journal of Offender Rehabilitation*, 31:1-2, 1-41.
- 5) Davis, L. M., Bozick, R., Steele, J., Saunders, J., & Miles, J. N. (2013). *Evaluating the Effectiveness of Correctional Education A Meta-Analysis of Programs That Provide Education to Incarcerated Adults*. RAND Corporation.
- 6) Lahm, K. F. (2000). Equal or Equitable. *Federal Probation*, 64(2),39-46.
- 7) Kuruppu, G. (2001, September). *Resource Material Series*. Retrieved February 12, 2020, from UNITED NATIONS ASIA AND FAR EAST INSTITUTE FOR THE PREVENTION OF CRIME AND THE TREATMENT OF OFFENDERS: https://www.unafei.or.jp/english/publications/Resource_Material_57.html
- 8) Davis, L. M., Bozick, R., Steele, J., Saunders, J., & Miles, J. N. (2013). *Evaluating the Effectiveness of Correctional Education A Meta-Analysis of Programs That Provide Education to Incarcerated Adults*. RAND Corporation.
- 9) Sachitra, V. and Wijewardhana, N. (2020), "The road to develop prisoners' skills and attitudes: an analytical study of contemporary prison-based rehabilitation programme in Sri Lanka", *Safer Communities*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SC-01-2019-0002>.
- 10) Smith, A., Balandin, S., Sigafoos, J., & Reed, V. A. (2009). The Kirkpatrick model: A useful tool for evaluating training outcomes. *Journal of Intellectual & Developmental Disability*, 34(3),266–274.
- 11) Shoham, E., Hasisi, B., Weisburd, D. L., & Haviv, N. (2017). The "Black Box" Behind Prison-Based Vocational Training. *European Scientific Journal*,13(12), 432-443.
- 12) Thailand Institute of Justice and Penal Reform International. (2019). *Guide to the rehabilitation and social reintegration of women prisoners*. London: Penal Reform International
- 13) Szifris, K., Fox, C., & Bradbury, A. (2018). A Realist Model of Prison Education, Growth, and Desistance: A New Theory. *Prison Education and Reentry*, 5(1), 41-60.
- 14) Tan, J. A., Hall, R. J., & Boyce, C. (2003). The Role of Employee Reactions in Predicting Training Effectiveness. *HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT QUARTERLY*, 14(4),397-411.
- 15) Tan, J. A., Hall, R. J., & Boyce, C. (2003). The Role of Employee Reactions in Predicting Training Effectiveness. *HUMAN RESOURCE DEVELOPMENT QUARTERLY*, 14(4),397-411.
- 16) Gordon, H. R., & Weldon, B. (2003). The Impact of Career and Technical Education Programs on Adult Offenders: Learning Behind Bars. *The Journal of Correctional Education*, 54(4), 200-209.
- 17) United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime. (2017). *Roadmap for the Development of Prison-based Rehabilitation Programmes*. Vienna: United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime.
- 18) Duwe, G. (2017). *The Use and Impact of Correctional Programming for Inmates on Pre- and Post-Release Outcomes*. Washington: National Institute of Justice.
- 19) Davis, L. M., Bozick, R., Steele, J., Saunders, J., & Miles, J. N. (2013). *Evaluating the Effectiveness of Correctional Education A Meta-Analysis of Programs That Provide Education to Incarcerated Adults*. RAND Corporation.
- 20) Sachitra, V. and Wijewardhana, N. (2020), "The road to develop prisoners' skills and attitudes: an analytical study of contemporary prison-based rehabilitation programme in Sri Lanka", *Safer Communities*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/SC-01-2019-0002>.